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Index of Abbreviations and Acronyms

APCARS - Association for Applied Criminal Policy and Social Reintegration
HIIF - Healthy Identity Intervention: Foundation
HIIP - Healthy Identity Intervention: Plus
LS-CMI - Level of Service/Case Management Inventory
NeDIC - Network for Deradicalisation in Corrections
NGO - Non-governmental organisation
NOMS - National Offender Management Service
RAN - Radicalisation Awareness Network
RIVE - Research and Intervention on Violent Extremism
RN - The Dutch Probation Service ('Reclassering Nederland')
TER - Terrorism, Extremism and Radicalisation team of the Dutch Probation Service
TUI - The Unity Initiative
UK - United Kingdom
VERA 2R - Violent Extremist Risk Assessment 2 Revised
VPN - Violence Prevention Network

Executive summary

The current report is part of the WayOut - “Integrated Exit Programme for Prison and Probation” projects’ Work Package 2 - state of art analysis (Review of exit strategies in prison and probation). Its aim is to map current exit programmes for prison and/or probation settings. Considering the goals and scope of the project, the programmes presented in this report are mostly from European Countries, representing institutional interventions that are implemented on a regular basis. The introduction of the report addresses key characteristics of exit programmes (i.e., who is the actor; what is the contact approach; and how relevant is the ideological component) as well as the range of interventions that can be part of these programmes (i.e., individual mentoring; mental health care and counselling; reintegration services). Section 2 of the report summarises exit programmes implemented in prisons. With a focus on the European reality, programmes in the United Kingdom (UK) (i.e., Healthy Identity Intervention), Denmark (i.e., Back on Track), Germany (i.e., Radicalisation Prevention and Deradicalisation in Prison and Probation - VPN; and Network for Deradicalisation in Corrections - Federal State of Hesse), Austria (i.e., De-radicalisation in Prisons), and Norway (i.e., Mentoring Scheme) are presented. Intervention programmes in prisons from other regions are also explored, with examples from Africa (i.e., Nigeria) and Middle East (i.e., Israel). Section 3 proceeds with examples from exit programmes in probation contexts in countries such as the UK (i.e., The Unity Initiative), France (i.e., Research and Intervention on Violent Extremism) and the Netherlands (i.e., Terrorism, Extremism and Radicalisation team of the Dutch Probation Service). Ending the report, the conclusions and what works section summarises the main findings of the previous sections, drawing conclusions based on the literature review (e.g., the need for multidisciplinary teams; tailor-made nature of the programmes; importance of a post-incarceration monitoring phase). Annex I summarises the described exit programmes in European Prisons.

1. Introduction

The aim of the current deliverable is to map current exit programmes that are being implemented both in prison and/or probation contexts in European Countries and other regions. Our focus will be on programmes that are institutionalised and being implemented regularly, meaning that stand-alone initiatives developed within projects that have a specific timeframe of implementation will not be considered. However, considering that programmes are usually financed on a one or two-year basis, information will be provided on programmes that are possibly no longer being financed but were implemented in a recent past.

Exit/de-radicalisation programmes should be part of a counter-terrorism architecture. They are an intervention strategy at micro-level thus targeting the individual (and the individuals' social environment whenever possible). According to Koehler (2017), three characteristics of individual intervention strategies can be found:

- (1) Actor - this first point is related to who runs the programme, such as governmental actors or non-governmental organisations (NGOs). According to the author, the type of actor running the action can “significantly influence the perception of the programme, its potential target group and its long-term success” (p. 71);
- (2) Contact approach - Kohler defines two different approaches: a passive and an active approach¹. When the programme develops proactive communication strategies to reach potential “clients” this is referred to as an active approach. On other hand, a passive approach means that the programme works “almost entirely with those persons who express an interest in leaving a group” (p. 72), that is, people with some degree of cognitive opening and a willingness to critically reflect on their actions;
- (3) Relevance of the ideological component - programmes can vary in the importance they attribute to the ideological component. Some of the programmes aim at challenging participants' ideology directly, while some regard the achievement of a cognitive change is a positive indirect effect of disengagement.

Regarding the length of these programmes, they are intensive, and last from 6 to 18 months (or even longer), involving a wide range of interventions, ideally starting during imprisonment. The Radicalisation Awareness Network (RAN) has identified the following methods of intervention (RAN, 2018):

- Individual mentoring and resilience training (e.g., working on critical thinking, relationship skills, empathy, self-esteem, responsibility and the ability to self-reflect);
- Specific conversation techniques, motivational interviewing, Socratic dialogue, moral dilemma discussion;
- Family support and community engagement;
- Mental health care and counselling;
- Religious/ideological counselling;
- Reintegration and employment services that help joining up social and economic support

¹ An active approach can be particularly useful to reach target groups and participants that otherwise will not be involved or even know about the existence of the programme. By implementing an active communication strategy, the programme wants to involve participants that engage with the intervention on a voluntary basis but aren't necessarily motivated to do so at first.

- for the individual;
- If applicable, removal of tattoos;
- Different tools (i.e., films, books and speakers) and visits to specific, relevant locations, arts or sports.

Regarding the first intervention mentioned in the list, mentoring interventions can be done by a variety of individuals, both professionals and volunteers², depending on the type of person and the given context (e.g., in prison, outside of prison). An important prerequisite is that the mentor is a credible role model that can build trust with the mentee. Other intervention methods are also being used such as the stabilisation coaching, implemented as a post-release measure in the Violence Prevention Network deradicalisation in prison programme (Violence Prevention Network, 2019).

The different methods mentioned above offer a wide range of strategies to implement in order to approach individuals, develop a relationship and initiate a higher tolerance of ambiguity to encourage a process of deradicalisation and to disengage them from violent actions. Both disengagement/distancing from violence and cognitive deradicalisation are vital parts of the reintegration and rehabilitation of (violent) extremist offenders.

Considering the complexity of setting up an exit intervention programme, RAN developed some recommendations related with the implementation of these interventions (Radicalisation Awareness Network, 2017). The recommendations fall on the following axes:

- Organisational structures and objectives: recommendations regarding the exit intervention's objectives (e.g., state the goal of the intervention, such as disengagement or deradicalisation), target group (e.g., right-wing extremists, Militant Islamists), type of intervention (e.g., programme, project or standard praxis), implementing organisation (i.e., if the programme is implemented by an NGO, governmental body or a public-private partnership), location of implementation (i.e., is the programme is implemented on a prison and probation setting or in society), and involvement of professionals / former extremists as mentors/coaches;
- Hiring staff: recommendations aligned with staff needs for these interventions (related to both personal characteristics (e.g., share some background with the target group) and KSA's (Knowledge, skills and attitudes; Exit worker must understand the radicalisation processes, believe that change is possible and be able to motivate people to change), and advantages and risks of including formers as staff members (i.e., increase credibility vs risk of relapse);
- Engaging with radicalised individuals: a set of topics that exit workers should be aware of, from what to (and not to) discuss with the participant (e.g., importance of questioning the participant and avoid moral judgement) to the creation of an environment that supports disengagement/deradicalisation (i.e., creating alternatives for the participant and build

² Regarding the use of volunteers in exit programmes, the partners are very sceptical about the advantages they may offer. Considering how demanding these interventions are in terms of time and skills needed it is questionable that the use of volunteers will bring benefits for the successful implementation of these interventions.

- social networks outside the extremist group);
- Guidelines on media/communication: related with crisis communication, guidelines for media appearances (e.g., being aware of confidentiality; being objective), and being proactive in seeking media attention (e.g., promote a good relationship with the media; share success stories this raising awareness and attracting both clients and funds);
- Confidentiality and security measures: this recommendation focus on the need to share information with different actors that play an important role in the intervention such as family members, police, local authorities while being aware of the privacy and confidentiality laws; Security measures are needed to protect the organisations involved, their staff and the participants/clients.
- Quality standards and evaluation: a set of measures that can be employed to improve the quality of the interventions and measure its success (e.g., define the target group, intervention goals and determine the processes that will be implemented).
- Returnees: the last topic is related to the concerns with foreign fighters, problematising aspects of this group, such as its heterogeneity and differences with other radical extremists.

Now aware of the characteristics of an exit intervention as well as recommended guidelines for its implementation, the current report will proceed as follows:

- **Section 2** summarises exit programmes in prison, with a focus on the European prisons' reality (2.1), but also learning with examples from other regions (2.2);
- **Section 3** outlines exit programmes currently being implemented in probation, considering the European reality;
- **Section 4** presents the main conclusions of the deliverable as well as an overview of what works.

2. Exit programmes in prison

The implementation of exit programmes in prisons is well recognised and recommended in literature (e.g., Jacobson, 2010). Considering the previously mentioned characteristics of deradicalisation/exit programmes, prison-based programmes are mostly part of governmental active programmes. According to Koehler (2017), these are the most common deradicalisation programmes and participants' involvement can vary in different regions, some of which are more coercive ones (in Middle East/ South Asia) while others are based on largely voluntary participation (Western World).

In the following subsection, we summarise several exit strategies that are being implemented in European prisons but also in other (non-European) countries. For the European practices, data was gathered from available scientific literature as well as RAN's "Preventing Radicalisation to Terrorism and Violent Extremism Approaches and Practices" (2018), that comprises an extensive collection of current practices and programmes throughout Europe. As previously defined in our literature review³, this report focus on exit programmes directly aiming at participants' deradicalisation, disengagement, reintegration and/or rehabilitation. Therefore, training programmes in the field of radicalisation and tools to assess radicalisation risk were not considered in the analysis.

2.1 Reality in European prisons

This section presents exit programmes implemented in European prison systems. We aim at being exhaustive in our analysis, thus presenting all available information about exit interventions implemented regularly⁴. French, Belgium and the Netherlands cases are also presented, even though no information was obtained regarding exit programmes being currently implemented, but only actions/initiatives aimed at tackling this issue.

In the **UK**, the "Healthy Identity Intervention" was developed as part of the PREVENT strategy implemented by the National Offender Management Service (NOMS). This intervention targets the criminogenic needs of terrorist/extremist inmates, that is, addressing the factors/circumstances that were directly related to the criminal activity. It aims at facilitating circumstances that encourage disengagement and desistance, as well as at addressing factors that make people engage in and act on behalf of a radical/terrorist organisation/activity (Dean, 2014). The Healthy Identity Intervention incorporates three models of offenders' rehabilitation:

- (1) Risk-Need-Responsivity model - a model that states that rehabilitation length should match offenders' risk and need level while targeting those at higher risk and with higher needs;
- (2) Factors that drive desistance - a model that tries to understand factors that lead offenders to divert from crime and then facilitate those processes through intervention;
- (3) Good Life model - that is based on the expectation that "offenders seek to satisfy the same needs or goods as non-offenders but it is how they seek to fulfil these which results in problematic and harmful behaviour"(Dean, 2014, p. 117).

³ For more information, please cf. WayOut WP2 D2.1 - State of art report.

⁴ Despite the mentioned aim, we are aware that information about programmes in this realm is likely to be maintained out of the public domain. Information about the interventions mentioned in this section was gathered in reports and scientific papers.

As the name implies, the construct of identity is key to this intervention. This is not surprising, since radicalisation factors are often connected with identity issues and radicalisation itself normally involves a change in ones' identity and beliefs structure. The intervention programme is delivered on a one-to-one basis, which turns the professional-inmate relationship crucial to its success. It uses several methods such as pro-social modelling, cognitive restructuring, identity development work, psycho-social education and opportunity creation. The intervention allows the exploration of beliefs, ideas and attitudes related with the criminal activity of the inmate. However, it does not aim at re-educating participants and the cognitive aspects of the programme are not ideologically based.

The Healthy Identity Intervention has two interrelated sub-programmes: the Healthy Identity Intervention: Foundation (HIIF), is considered a low intensity intervention, comprising three modules and targeting inmates that only had superficial contact with terrorist groups; and the Healthy Identity Intervention: Plus (HIIP), a medium to high intensity intervention comprising seven modules. Both interventions were summarised by Dean (2014). HIIF modules are:

- *Engagement & Insight sessions*: helps participants explore what is important in their lives and how can they fulfil their needs without offending (or engaging in extremist groups);
- *Mindfulness sessions*: sessions that help inmates cope with thoughts and feelings that affect them every day (such as feelings of injustice and grievance);
- *Moving On sessions*: help inmates create new ways for their lives, aligned with their values, beliefs and needs.

The more complex intervention (HIIP) comprises the following modules:

- *Foundation sessions*: these sessions are a first exploration on inmates' identity, helping them to understand why they started their involvement with terrorist groups/offending behaviour;
- *Personal Identity sessions*: sessions that allow participants to reflect on decisions/commitments they made. Participants are also expected to reflect on alternative commitments, aligned with their identity but harmless to others;
- *Group involvement sessions*: inmates should explore the nature of their relationship with the group(s) they committed with, including the negative aspects and losses they face related with that, thus supporting new involvements that may support disengagement;
- *Self-image sessions*: in these sessions, inmates explore their self-image and the changes they can make in their lives in order to preserve their self-image without engage in radical/terrorist action/groups;
- *Group Conflict sessions*: sessions that help participants develop alternative strategies to face threats, while trying to reduce black and white thinking;
- *Seeking Change sessions*: these sessions challenge the legitimacy of inmates' terrorist actions, helping them on achieving goals or expressing their values by legitimate means;
- *Concluding sessions*: sessions to help inmates reflect on the progress they done so far while consolidating strategies to move forward.

In **Denmark**, “Back on Track” project is being implemented by the Danish Prison and Probation Service and aims to “develop and test mentoring schemes as a tool to support inmates in leaving

far-right, far-left or religious extremism behind” (Butt & Tuck, 2014, p. 16). Targeting inmates that were/are somehow related to extremist groups or terrorist/hate crimes, this programme uses mentoring schemes to assist these individuals during their deradicalisation and distancing processes. The programme was framed on an existing mentoring action in prison and incorporates a training component, in which 3 out of the 13 existing mentors can train/coach other mentors. Through the mentor’s intervention, the project intends to help inmates dealing with everyday situations, adopting a lifestyle free of crime, while involving inmates’ networks outside prison and supporting inmates in specific activities (such as job seeking activities) (RAN, 2018).

In **Belgium**, 450 radicals (of which 130 convicted terrorists) were serving sentences in 2018 of which 132 were receiving some form of support and 68 started an individual deradicalisation path (Dumoulin, 2019). Some measures were taken during the last years, such as the isolation of proselytist inmates and monitoring of inmates considered vulnerable to radicalisation. Regarding prisons staff, investment in training was made with more than 400 staff members engaging in training on the topic of radicalisation and 70 specialists having further in-depth training on the topic (Dumoulin, 2019). However, as of June 2018, no deradicalisation/disengagement programme existed in Belgium (Dumoulin, 2019).

In **France**, data from May 2018 states that 1200 radical inmates were being managed in French prisons, of which 500 were convicted terrorists. Inmates placement is decided by the prison administration after evaluating inmates’ dangerousness (which takes up to 4 months). A research programme aiming at working with inmates (reflecting on their violent paths; creating gaps and uncertainty on their discourse) was implemented from January 2015 to March 2016, reaching 80 participants, of which 51 were accompanied on a voluntary basis (Dumoulin, 2019).

In **the Netherlands** two prisons (Vught and Rotterdam) have specialised terrorist wings for extremist offenders. Extremist offenders are categorised and placed in different terrorist wings. Leaders and followers are separated. Other variables, such as gender, degree of frustration and influence ability are relevant for the placement of the extremist offenders as well. Information is collected upon the arrival of an offender to get a clear picture of the offender and his situation (e.g. a risk-assessment report is provided by the probation services ‘Reclassering Nederland’). The information gathered makes it possible to create a risk profile, select the appropriate location for placement and devise an individual approach (Dienst Justitiële Inrichtingen, 2019). For the WayOut project a visit was made to the location in Vught. In an interview the director and psychologist explained that a tailor-made approach in working with extremist offenders was preferable. Reducing the most prominent risk factors, paying attention to protective factors, building a relationship of trust with the offender, a systems approach (involving family) and working closely together with other organisations concerning an offender’s reintegration were, besides other things, seen as important and focused on in prison. The psychologist played an important role in this. The activities in the Dutch prisons surrounding the work with extremist offenders are in here conveniently interpreted as an exit programme. It concerns a set of strategies employed by professionals to produce behavioural change (del. 2.1). In the Netherlands these activities are formally not labelled as an exit programme.

Developed in **Germany** by Violence Prevention Network (VPN), the project “Radicalisation Prevention and Deradicalisation in Prison and Probation” targets inmates who are sympathisers, supporters and members of extremist groups, are radicalised with or without violent intent or

have committed ideologically motivated violent acts.

VPN approaches offenders that have already expressed the wish to disengage from the extremist milieu as well as individuals who have not yet questioned their ideological beliefs or who are in the process of radicalising. By offering non-confrontational individual as well as group sessions, the programme supports them in stepping away from violence and in challenging and abandoning extremist ideologies. The goal of the programme is that participants distance themselves from extremist and anti-democratic ideologies and refrain from using violence. Moreover, participants are encouraged to recognise the dignity of others, shown non-violent ways of solving conflicts and learn to take responsibility for their own actions. In order to better understand their own behaviour, the participants' biographies are an essential part of the session and they are empowered through actively planning and creating a future for themselves (Violence Prevention Network, 2019). Furthermore, the programme also workshops for prison/probation and judicial staff to sensitising them regarding signs of radicalisation and sees them as multipliers and secondary beneficiaries of the programme.

The programme is currently being implemented in several federal states in Germany and aims to work the following skills with inmates (RAN, 2018, p. 165):

- “Relationship skills, empathy, self-esteem, capacity for self-reflection;
- To distance themselves from inhumane hate ideologies;
- To better understand and correct their violent behaviour;
- To accept everyone’s fundamental right to liberty and freedom from bodily harm;
- To learn how to resolve conflict non-violently;
- To take responsibility for their actions;
- To play an active role in planning their future”.

An evaluation of the programme that compared recidivism rates for violent ideological motivated offenses (using data from 188 right-wing participants) of participants and non-participants on the programme, shows that reincarceration rates are 68% lower for those who participated.

Also in Germany, more precisely in the Federal State of Hesse, the programme called “NeDiC - Network for Deradicalisation in Corrections” is implemented. Responsibilities of the Network are organised in four main stages:

- (1) Identification - comprises the monitoring and information gathering of extremist prisoners by trained correctional officers (Structural observers);
- (2) Prevention - this pillar aims to improve cooperation between multiple agencies (e.g., correctional staff, NGOs, Imams, the Hessian Ministry of Justice, the Hessian Criminal Police, and the Hessian Office for the Protection of the Constitution); Observation work done by structural observers and other correctional staff contributes to dynamic security;
- (3) Deradicalisation - in this stage, although deradicalisation is a goal, priority is given to disengagement from violent extremism. Intervention with extremist prisoners may include reduction of individual radicalisation factors; individual and group-based de-radicalisation programmes (provided by violent extremism network); anti-violence training; psychotherapy; and teaching of democratic values;
- (4) Coordination - includes the overall coordination of the programme, education of staff, exchange of information with security agencies.

Until now, no formal evaluation of the programme has taken place. However, practitioners have identified certain activities that have been particularly successful such as raising awareness of symbols of extremists or educating staff about extremist ideologies (RAN, 2018).

In **Austria**, within the frame of the “De-radicalisation in Prisons” action of the Austrian Government, the Austrian NGO DERAD aims to tackle Salafism using methods “based on history, al-Aqida, fiqh, manhaj, pedagogy, history and civic education” (RAN, 2018, p. 594). This means, that the project uses counter- and alternative narratives to combat the Salafist ideology. It is implemented in the prison and probation setting as well as outside of prison in non-legal contexts, for instance in networks that consist of radicalised individuals.

In **Norway**, the Ministry of Justice and Public Security’s action plan against radicalisation and violent extremism (2014) proposed the implementation of a Mentoring scheme in the Norwegian Correctional Services as part of the strategy to prevent the growth of extremist groups and help promote reintegration (Orban, 2019). The mentoring scheme focuses on identified inmates convicted of hate crimes, who are understood to be vulnerable to violent extremism, especially young inmates. Individuals with the following risk factors are considered vulnerable: i) lack of education; ii) lack of work experience; iii) criminal record; iv) lack of affiliation; v) lack of social networks; vi) little or no contact with family; vii) drug and alcohol abuse; viii) gang belonging; vi) others. Despite the programme not being compulsory, prison staff is encouraged to work towards inmate’s motivation to participate.

The main objectives of the Mentoring Programme are (Orban, 2019): 1) to prevent prisoners from using or encouraging others to use violence to achieve their political and religious goals; 2) to prevent inmates from making contact or developing networks with people in violent extremist groups; and 3) to intervene in the processes in which a person increasingly accepts the use of violence.

Regarding effectiveness of the programmes, some articles in newspapers show that inmates’ engagement in programmes is hard to be achieved as well as effective de-radicalisation, therefore calling for post-release active monitoring⁵. However, we should rely on scientific research to make statements about effectiveness of exit interventions that, to date, is very limited in this realm and therefore does not allow us neither to accept nor reject these statements.

2.2 Reality in other regions

In **Nigeria**, a deradicalisation programme was developed for use in prisons, encompassing the following four iterative stages (Barkindo & Bryans, 2016).

- (1) Engagement - In which professionals get to know the VEO, gain their trust and establish a professional link;
- (2) Risk assessment - the caseworker from the treatment team performs a risk assessment to know more about inmates’ motives to become violent extremists as well as to assess the

⁵ UK: <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/uk/home-news/terrorist-prisoners-majority-refused-deradicalisation-now-free-on-streets-a7390821.html>

Spain: <https://www.elperiodico.com/es/politica/20180818/atentados-barcelona-cambriils-plan-desradicalizacion-no-ablanda-yihadistas-6993378>

- risk they currently represent;
- (3) Needs assessment - in the third stage, professionals evaluate needs related with risk in order to further reduce engagement in violent activities;
 - (4) Interventions/response - implementation of interventions to reduce previously identified risks.

Regarding the intervention methods used, seven different interventions relevant to the Nigerian context were developed: (1) motivational interviewing; (2) vocational training and work experience; (3) education and cultural activities; (4) art therapy; (5) sports and games; (6) religious interventions; and (7) psychological and counselling interventions.

Success of the programme has been measured with recidivism rates. However, Clubb and Tapley (2018) argue that recidivism has several problems as a success indicator (e.g., critics regarding a causal relationship between ideology and violent behaviour; lack of programmes' capacity and infrastructure to measure recidivism), and that the success of exit programmes will depend more on the (former) inmate's reintegration in a given societal context.

An example from **Israel** was also found in the literature and is presented here. We should take into account the highly securitised approach that is followed by Israeli authorities. The Israeli Prison Service incarcerates thousands of inmates (considered security prisoners - 7.300 in 2009) that are already radicalised when they enter the prison facilities (Ganor & Falk, 2013). Most of those inmates were incarcerated for murder (or attempted murder) and relate to groups such as Fatah, Hamas, Islamic Jihad or the Popular Front. In prison, they are segregated according to their affiliation. The main prison wings (Fatah, Hamas and Islamic Jihad) elect a spokesperson that translate orders and prison instructions. One central spokesperson represents inmates to the prison authorities. Without giving much information on current de-radicalisation efforts, the cited reference presents some challenges to deradicalisation programmes in these settings, such as the need to segregate inmates that want to engage in these programmes, since “a prisoner who participates in any de-radicalisation program against the orders of his organisation and peer group may face severe consequences” (Ganor & Falk, 2013, p. 126).

3. Exit programmes in probation

Probation context is a challenging one, considering that when inmates are released probation services should ensure the support needed, while at the same time manage the risk of them engaging in violent extremism, therefore calling for multi-agency cooperation (prison, probation, police, and community service providers) (RANP&P, 2016). The Prison and Probation working group of RAN has defined some good practices when it comes to release and integrate violent extremist offenders, namely, the need for continuity of support to the person in probation (considering high risk of recidivism) and the need for multi-agency cooperation to smooth the transition period from prison to community.

3.1. Reality in Europe

When compared with deradicalisation programmes in other regions (such as Middle East and Asia), programmes in European countries “place less emphasis on ideology and instead focus on practical and economic assistance in connection with exit, on psychological counselling, as well as assistance with forming new social ties outside the extremist group” (Dalgaard-Nielsen, 2013, p. 100). Considering the nature of these programmes, the most used success indicator is behavioural disengagement, meaning that the attendee stays away from crime. This is interesting and shows a change in the “European” approach that, from a historical standpoint, used to put a stronger emphasis on ideology (Neumann, 2013). In fact, currently in Europe, when we talk about intervention programmes, it seems that no agreement exists about what approach is more efficient or, as Bouzar (2017) states, “while some say that radical ideas are not a social issue as long as they do not lead to terrorist acts, others believe that to tackle terrorist acts, one must address the underlying ideology” (p. 612).

In the UK, The Unity Initiative (TUI) aims to tackle violent extremism and rehabilitate terrorist offenders through the development of critical thinking skills. TUI also provides training for prisons’ frontline staff. According to TUI, they have successfully rehabilitated high profile terrorists and are contacted by terrorists that search for ideological rehabilitation (RAN, 2018).

A mentoring approach was also used in the **French** project RIVE⁶ (Research and Intervention on Violent Extremism), applied in Paris and Paris Region by the NGO Association for Applied Criminal Policy and Social Reintegration (APCARS⁷). The project seeks to involve violent extremist probationers. Lasting no less than one year, participation in RIVE is mandatory⁸ (judicial obligation). RIVE aims to de-radicalise participants through “a social, healthcare, psychological and professional intervention undertaken in order to ensure the social reintegration of offenders and the acquisition of the value of citizenship” (RAN, 2018, p. 151). Implementation is done by a

⁶ Please note that the implementation of RIVE was terminated during 2019. However, we keep the description of the programme as it represents an interesting example of a public-private partnership.

⁷ <http://www.apcars.fr/lutter-contre-la-radicalisation-violente/>

⁸ The efficacy of mandatory interventions is questionable, since we can argue that “Desistance, disengagement and de-radicalisation will only be legitimately sustained if those who commit to the programme do so of their own free will” (Barkindo & Bryans, 2016, pp. 21-22).

multidisciplinary team of educators, psychologists, religious counsellors, psychiatrists and a criminal lawyer educated to doctorate level. Each social worker works with a maximum of 5 probationers. Intervention is individual and assessment is done with tools such as the Level of Service/Case Management Inventory (LS-CMI) and The Violent Extremist Risk Assessment 2 Revised (Vera 2R) in order to work on an individual plan.

In the **Netherlands** three probation services exist. The Dutch Probation Service ('Reclassering Nederland', RN) works with people who are suspected or convicted for offences related to terrorism, or who show signs of radicalisation under regular probation oversight. Within RN a specialised unit became active in 2012, 'team TER' (Terrorism, Extremism and Radicalisation). Team TER is responsible for (1) advisory reports on clients (risk assessment, strategies to reduce recidivism, etc.) and (2) supervising clients (monitoring probation requirements). These tasks are in line with regular probation work and the team can use all the tools within the organisation that support these tasks (different risk assessment tools, protocols, electronic monitoring systems, etc.). The approach of team TER differs from regular probation work on the following points:

- Both tasks (reporting and supervising) are done by the same team members;
- The team starts its work with incarcerated clients in an earlier stage;
- Each client is supervised by two team members to ensure a proper assessment of the client and his behaviour;
- Bi-weekly meetings are held to discuss clients, share experiences and invite experts to increase the team's expertise;
- Team members are trained on theological/ideological matters;
- Theologians are used in client contact to help them reflect on their world view;
- The VERA-2R risk assessment tool is used. The tool focuses on radicalisation;
- Some team members are trained in a cognitive skills method that addresses the risk of recidivism among radicalised clients. The method is called 'Inclusion' and comprises three modules: (1) practical help - client defines future goals, personal problems can be tackled, and a working alliance is build; (2) network approach - mapping of client prosocial networks to find a significant other; and (3) cognitive behavioural training - exercises to train topics such as impulsivity, values, social skills, and thinking patterns.

The approach of team TER is pragmatic and flexible. Building a good working relationship with clients is seen as especially important. Team TER is concerned with reducing recidivism and focuses on both de-radicalisation and disengagement. The approach has been the subject of an in-depth evaluation. The underpinnings of the approach were proper but operationalising success and gathering data to measure this was somewhat problematic (van der Heide & Schuurman, 2018).

In **Belgium**, under the radicalism action plan, the creation of the Local Integral Security Cells - cellules de sécurité intégrales locales (CSIL) - was started in July 2018. As of January 2019, the majority of Belgium communities (589 on total) have their own cell working as a local platform that allows the social prevention services, administration and civil society actors to address cases of radicalisation (Dumoulin, 2019).

4. Conclusions and what works

The current WayOut deliverable presented exit strategies that are being implemented in prisons and/or probation contexts in different latitudes. It started with a reflection on the characteristics of intervention programmes, namely who is the actor (governmental vs NGOs), what is the contact approach of the programme (passive vs active) and which relevance is given to the ideological component. The programmes that were mapped allowed us to provide an overview of the current reality in European countries, as well as examples of programmes from outside of Europe.

The analysis of exit strategies implemented in different countries and regions helped us to understand some basic principles common to these programmes, as well as some frequent problems and difficulties related with the implementation and assessment of these programmes. From the current literature review we can state that:

- Exit strategies should be implemented by a multidisciplinary team;
- Programmes should be individual, targeting inmates/probationers' specific needs and risks;
- Participation on the programme should be voluntary. In some cases, rewards can be associated to the successful completion of the programme;
- Building a constructive professional relationship between inmate/probationer and member(s) of the intervention team is key to the execution of the programme;
- When considering programmes developed in prison, a post-reincarceration monitoring of former inmates is key. Therefore, multiagency cooperation is essential to ensure effective rehabilitation of radicalised inmates.

These conclusions will be key to the development of our framework to assess exit programmes. That is, the basic principles that were here summarised, can represent important attributes of exit programmes that need to be assessed.

5. Annexes

Annex I

Country (Author/Organisation)	Name of intervention programme	Type of intervention	Main goals	Intervention Methodology
UK (NOMS)	Healthy Identity Intervention (Foundation; Plus)	Disengagement; de-radicalisation; rehabilitation	To change inmates' identity and beliefs structure	One-to-one intervention
Denmark (Danish Prison and Probation service)	Back on Track	De-radicalisation; Reintegration	To promote autonomy and integration in society	Mentoring-based intervention
Germany (VPN)	Radicalisation prevention and deradicalisation in prison and probation	De-radicalisation; Disengagement	To develop pro-social skills	
Germany (Federal State of Hesse)	NeDIC - Network for Deradicalisation in Corrections	Disengagement; De-radicalisation	To promote inmates' disengagement from violent extremism	Training programme for staff; Individual and group-based intervention with inmates
Austria (DERAD)	De-radicalisation in Prisons	De-radicalisation	To prevent violent extremism	Counter-narratives
Norway (Norwegian Correctional Services)	Mentoring Scheme	Deradicalisation; disengagement	To prevent the use of violence to achieve political/religious goals; preventing inmates' network development with extremist groups; intervene during the radicalisation process	Mentoring

Table 1 - Summary of current exit programmes in European prisons

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